

IDENTIFYING CHILDREN WITH AUTISM SPECTRUM DISORDER (ASD) AMONG MAINSTREAM PRESCHOOL TEACHERS IN KLANG VALLEY

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ABSTRACT

Malaysia, along with many other countries, made a pledge to all children to ensure that all their rights including the rights to education will be protected and promoted when the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) was adopted. In line with that, inclusive education was introduced in the Education Act 1996 and has been established ever since. According to the Malaysian Education Blueprint (2013-2025), the goal was to have children of 5 years registered in a preschool whether if it is public or private because the period from birth to five years is extremely crucial for any child as these are vital in laying the foundation for children to nurture their cognitive, language, physical, social, emotional, behavioral development. This study investigates the knowledge level of mainstream preschool teachers in identifying children with ASD. By focusing on teachers' knowledge, the research aims to provide a better understanding of the promotion of inclusive education in Malaysia's preschools. A mixed-method approach was used in this study. 30 respondents who worked in the field of early childhood education were recruited for this study. An online questionnaire was sent out for respondents to answer. Six respondents were recruited for the interview session that followed. Findings show that the knowledge level of the respondents ranges between moderate to high with the majority having a high knowledge level. The findings also resulted that one of the most important factors that affect the respondents' knowledge in identifying children with ASD is through hands-on experiences and training related to ASD. This study implies that mainstream preschool teachers need to be exposed to ASD children so that they can have hands-on experiences, which will further strengthen their knowledge on ASD to ensure that they can identify children with ASD in the future.

Keywords: Inclusive education, autism spectrum disorder

INTRODUCTION

According to Ministry of Health (MOH) data, the number of diagnoses for autism spectrum disorder (ASD) in Malaysia have risen steadily over the past decade (CodeBlue, 2022). As stated in the DSM 5, autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is defined as persistent deficits in social communication and social interaction across context that are not accounted for by general developmental delays (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). In the report by the Special Education Division, the number of autistic children enrolled at a preschool level in the Malaysian education system as of 2020 was 605 students.

Ideally, early childhood educators should know the early symptoms of ASD in preschool children because early childhood educators are one of the closest adults to children other than the immediate family. Thus, early childhood educators are more likely to notice developmental delays in children and therefore must have the knowledge of ASD to identify children with ASD. (Qi et al., 2016). When symptoms are identified early, these children can be referred to specialists and early intervention can be made. Early interventions may be in the form of special support to help guide these children. The Straits Times (2019) newspaper proposed that skills and knowledge about inclusion should be taught to mainstream preschool teachers (MPT) so that they can help with early interventions in their preschool.

The National Association for the Education of Young Children (NAEYC) code of ethical responsibility mentioned in the ideal that early childhood educators should be able to assess children and use the assessed information to identify children who may need extra help (Feeney et. al, 2022). This indicates that it is the ethical responsibility of MPT to know about identifying children with ASD. However, not all MPT can identify the symptoms of ASD in children. Taresh et al (2019) reported that the knowledge of ASD symptoms in preschool teachers was generally low. It can be argued that although with an appropriate qualification and teaching experience, it still does not necessarily mean that they have the knowledge to identify ASD children.

Problem Statement

When MPT are not able to identify the symptoms of ASD, there will be a few consequences. The specific child would always be left behind or not included in class activities. This will only lead to the child's further delay in learning and social development when the child would not receive the appropriate interventions. When these children are not identified early and given early interventions, their future stages of development will also be affected. Thus, when ASD children are not given appropriate help in these areas, their social and emotional development will not be facilitated, and this may lead them to face even more difficulties socializing with people and expressing what they want. Thus, there is a need to find out the factors that affect MPT knowledge in identifying children with ASD and this is the gap that needs to be investigated as the ideal was supposed to be that all MPT should be able to identify the symptoms of ASD children.

Research Questions

- 1) What is the knowledge level of mainstream preschool teachers in identifying children with ASD?
- 2) What are the factors that affect mainstream preschool teachers' knowledge in identifying children with ASD?

Research Objectives

- 1) To identify the knowledge level of mainstream preschool teachers in identifying children with ASD.
- 2) To identify the factors that affect mainstream preschool teachers' knowledge in identifying children with ASD.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Liu et al., (2016) researched the knowledge, attitudes, and perceptions of autism spectrum disorder among 471 preschool teachers in China. Findings reported that 83% of the respondents were not able to correctly answer the questionnaire on the knowledge of ASD. Most of the respondents thought that ASD is related to psychological issues and ASD can be cured if children receive treatment at a young age. The results revealed that respondents with early childhood development education had a greater significance in preschool teachers' knowledge of ASD compared to the ones without. Similarly, Yunus and Mohamed (2019) studied the competencies of preschool teachers in identifying children at risk of learning disabilities within 12 preschools located in Kuala Lumpur, Selangor and Federal Territory Putrajaya to find that most of the respondents' competencies were low.

This similarity shows that preschool teachers with training in early childhood education had more knowledge on ASD and that preschool teachers with previous work experiences with special needs also have higher knowledge in identifying ASD. However, what was not studied was the relationship between preschool teachers' work experience without special needs and the knowledge of identifying ASD. This emphasizes that there is a need for investigation to be done to know if work experiences can affect the knowledge level of identifying children with special needs in mainstream preschool teachers. This is so that the gap can be narrowed and can help future researchers to find out if there is a need to include working experiences with ASD children during teacher training.

Taresh et al. (2020) conducted a study on the ability of mainstream preschool teachers to identify children with ASD which involved 20 mainstream preschool teachers using the mixed-method approach. It was revealed that only 25% of the MPT could accurately identify that the child has ASD. Demographic factors such as age, education level and teaching experiences do not have any significant impact on the respondents' ability to identify children with ASD. A difference is seen here when compared to the reviewed literature above whereby the former indicated that education level influences their knowledge level, but the latter study differs in findings.

Since several factors can affect preschool teachers' knowledge in identifying children with ASD, there is a need to identify the factors that can affect preschool teachers' knowledge in identifying ASD. The significance of this study is to increase the awareness of the importance of preschool teachers to have knowledge about children with ASD so that they can identify children with ASD that enter their classroom.

METHODOLOGY

Methodology and Participants

This research employed a mixed-method approach. Mixed-method research is used because it can reflect the participants' opinion and this is to also retrieve information based on their experiences (Wisdom & Cresswell, 2013). The methods employed were questionnaire and interview. Research question one was investigated via a questionnaire where the symptoms of ASD children were examined. The questionnaire was adopted from Grattan (2017) and Drusch (2015). 30 participants consisting of both principals and preschool teachers were recruited for this study. All these participants were within Klang Valley. Research question two was investigated via an interview whereby regarding about the factors that affect preschool teachers' knowledge in identifying children with ASD. As for the interview, 6 participants who volunteered themselves in the questionnaire were then approached.

Data collection

The questionnaire was created using Google Forms and shared online with the participants. Participants who were interested in volunteering for the interview session were asked to provide their contact details. Upon the completion of the questionnaire, the six participants were contacted telephonically. Once the interviewees were finalized, an appointment was made with each interviewee where a date and time was set up for the interview session. Each interview session lasted between 30 minutes to 1 hour. All the interview sessions were carried out through Zoom platform.

Data analysis

For the questionnaire, a 5-point Likert Scale (with 1 being strongly disagree and 5 being strongly agree) was used to measure the respondents' knowledge in identifying the symptoms of ASD. The responses were then totaled up. The total would be indicative of the overall level of knowledge of the respondents. As for the interviews, thematic analysis was used where the participants' answers were coded, and themes were made to answer the research question.

RESULTS AND FINDING

The knowledge level of mainstream preschool teachers in identifying children with ASD

Results revealed majority of the participants responded correctly. All the participants answered at least 50% of the questions correctly. The respondents' knowledge level in identifying symptoms of ASD ranged between moderate to high indicating that the knowledge in identifying the symptoms in ASD children among these participants are high. The overall results are shown in Table 1.

Total score (Level of knowledge)	Number of participants
Low (17-39)	0
Moderate (40-62)	9
High (63-85)	21

Table 1: Level of ASD knowledge among MPT

Factors that affect mainstream preschool teachers' knowledge in identifying children with ASD

The findings found that there are five main factors which are training, attitude, availability of information, interest in ASD and working experiences. The most important factor that helped the interviewees in gaining their knowledge to identify ASD children was from hands-on experiences and talking to people who were involved in dealing with ASD children. The factors are as depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Factors affecting mainstream preschool teachers ASD knowledge

Training

The interviewees reported training received was (i) subjects that were related to ASD during their teacher training courses; (ii) workshop organized by institutions and workplaces. These interviewees that received training remembered learning about the definition of ASD and the symptoms or characteristics of ASD, challenges faced by ASD children. It was reported that the training received was useful and that it helps them to understand more about ASD children as well as to identify ASD children.

Attitude

It was reported that the early childhood education course does not go into detail about ASD and because of this, teachers face challenges such as not being able to identify the problem, provide appropriate intervention and explain to parents. Despite that, all interviewees reported a positive attitude towards wanting to gain in-depth knowledge about ASD. The answers that were reported was, (i) willingness to attend training due to personal interest in knowing more about children with ASD as they were exposed to these children before and would like to help these children; (ii) willingness to network with professionals who are able to make interventions for ASD children so that they can be approached; (iii) willingness to work hand in hand with parents and caregivers with the in depth knowledge that they possess.

Availability of information

The third factor that affects mainstream preschool teachers' knowledge level of ASD is the availability of information from alternative sources. All the interviewees reported that they will look for information by themselves through online articles and from other individuals based on the type of information that they need. The modes of receiving information that was stated were Facebook news, articles and stories that are shared on social medias by organizations, Google, blogs about ASD, follow families on social media that shares their experiences dealing with ASD children, friends and colleagues that are in working specifically with special needs children.

Interest in ASD

All interviewees reported that the interest in ASD leads them to gain more knowledge. It was stated that the current level of knowledge is not always sufficient to help the relevant children or assist parents. All the interviewees reported that with the in-depth knowledge, they are keen to help the ASD children to reach their optimum capabilities.

Working experience

Working experience was reported to be a factor however to a varying range. Two interviewees reported not being able to gain any information on ASD from their working experiences due to limited number of autistic children in her classroom whereby the children demonstrated similar traits. The other four interviewees agreed that they gained information on ASD through their working experiences via information sharing between colleagues, dealing with children of various spectrum.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In the research by Yunus and Mohamed (2019), the results show that the preschool teachers' competencies in identifying the children were low. They did investigate whether early childhood education training was a factor in determining the preschool teachers' competencies and it turns out that there was a significant difference. However, when compared to this current research, the participants' educational level in early childhood education does not affect their knowledge in identifying children with ASD. This may be due to the reason not all of them were exposed to subjects related to ASD during their teacher training whether if it is at diploma or degree levels. Thus, the educational level does not affect the participants' knowledge, but it would rather be more on the contents being taught during the education or teacher training received. This is why the ASD subjects that the participants were exposed to during their teacher training was said to help them in gaining this knowledge in identifying children with ASD.

Yunus and Mohamed (2019) also concluded that the working experiences did not affect the teachers' competencies in identifying the children which is also supported in this finding whereby the number of working experiences did not affect their knowledge but what the participants gained from the working experiences did help them to gain information on the ASD. This is because the participants mentioned that when they deal with the children, they remember better hence the reason why the number of years of working experiences does not affect the knowledge in identifying may be because the participants did not come across many children with ASD, so they were not exposed. However, if the participants did deal with the children before, they are able to remember the symptoms shown because of their experiences.

A similar finding was linked to the study by Taresh et al (2020) where a conclusion was made that MPT need training on ASD so that they can increase their awareness and knowledge. All interviewees in this study said that they would attend the seminars on ASD if they were provided with the opportunity and this shows that the interviewees portrayed a positive attitude towards wanting to learn more about ASD.

From the data collected, all the interviewees that were exposed to subjects related to ASD during their early childhood education training except for one, revealed that the contents learnt was useful for them to identify children with ASD. Thus, it is safe to say that it is important for preschool teachers to be exposed to subjects or contents related to ASD to increase their knowledge so that they can identify children with ASD and explain to parents about the condition so that the parents can have the children to be checked. Besides, another reason to why these participants generally have a high knowledge level is because each of them have a positive attitude as all of them would go for seminars because they want to gain new information about ASD to help the children if they if they come across any child with ASD. Thus, this can also conclude that preschool teachers need to be exposed to and given the opportunity to deal with ASD children during their teacher training or at any point of a time to give them the hands-on experiences.

One limitation of this study is that only 30 respondents were recruited and of that only six were interviewed. Moreover, the selected respondents are only from Klang Valley. The sample size is small, which does not allow the results of this study to be generalized for all the preschool teachers.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the results of this entire study have shown that the knowledge level of MPT in identifying children with ASD is high. The main factors that help the involved interviewees in gaining knowledge about ASD and remembering the symptoms about ASD is through hands-on experiences and training related to ASD did help the interviewees as well. Thus, this shows that all teacher training courses, specifically early childhood education, should contain subjects related to ASD and other common special needs so that preschool teachers to be would have the basic knowledge. In addition to this, MPT to be should also be exposed to ASD children so that they can have opportunities for hands-on experiences, which will further strengthen their knowledge on ASD to ensure that they have the basic knowledge to identify children with ASD when they come across one.

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